

Exploring the Relationship Between Teachers' Stress Management and Performance

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Abstract

This study explored how teachers manage stress and how it relates to their teaching performance among public school teachers in a district of the Negros Island Region for the 2023–2024 school year. Researchers gathered data from 223 teachers chosen through stratified random sampling. Stress management was measured using a standardized questionnaire based on Lazarus and Folkman's stress and coping framework, and teaching performance was assessed using teachers' IPCRF ratings. The analysis used descriptive statistics, the Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis H test, and Spearman rho. The results showed that teachers managed stress well, most often using relaxation and problem-solving strategies. Few teachers sought professional help. Teaching performance was rated as outstanding for all groups. There were no significant differences in stress management or teaching performance based on age or civil status, but teaching performance did differ by the level taught. The study also found no significant link between stress management and teaching performance. The study concludes that teachers perform well even with different ways of managing stress. This may be due to their resilience, motivation, and coping strategies shaped by culture. The findings help explain what makes teachers effective and highlight the need for support programs that improve well-being, even if they do not directly affect performance.

Keywords: *Teachers' Stress Management, Teaching Performance, Public School Teachers, Coping Strategies, Work-Related Stress*

Introduction

Nature of the Problem

Teaching is a demanding job that calls for ongoing mental, emotional, and social effort. Teachers must work with students from different backgrounds, follow curriculum guidelines, handle paperwork, and adapt to changes in education. These responsibilities can create stress that affects how well teachers do their jobs. If stress is not managed, it can cause tiredness, lower motivation, and reduce the quality of teaching. However, managing stress well helps teachers stay focused, keep their emotions in check, and be productive, which leads to better teaching. Recent research shows that when teachers do not manage work-related stress, they are more likely to experience burnout and perform worse at work. This highlights why stress management is an important skill for teachers (Agyapong et al., 2022; Collie, 2021).

Teacher performance is a key issue in education because it affects how well students learn and how schools function overall. Effective teachers have strong subject knowledge, good teaching skills, and can build supportive classrooms. But stress can get in the way by making it harder to focus, make decisions, and manage the classroom. Studies show that teachers under a lot of stress are less effective and perform worse in their jobs, while those who use healthy coping strategies tend to do better (von der Embse et al., 2019). This shows why it is important to understand how managing stress can help teachers maintain and improve their performance.

Teachers in the Philippines face their own particular problems, which create additional work demands due to the need to manage large student groups, extensive teaching requirements, school duties, and a lack of teaching materials. The basic education system faces increased operational requirements due to ongoing curriculum reforms and separate accountability measures. The importance of this research study lies in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, which establish teacher quality standards across multiple areas, including content knowledge, teaching methods, learning environments, and personal development and professional advancement. Teachers need to control their stress levels because this ability directly affects their teaching performance and their ability to meet professional standards. Therefore, stress management research is needed because it helps teachers maintain their national standard of performance (DepEd, 2017). Moreover, this study aligns with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4, which emphasizes the provision of inclusive and equitable quality education and the promotion of lifelong learning opportunities. Ensuring teachers' well-being through effective stress management is essential to achieving this goal, as teacher performance is a key determinant of educational quality (United Nations, 2015).

Although teacher well-being is getting more attention, few studies in the Philippines examine how stress management affects teachers' performance. Most research focuses on stress or performance separately, and only a few examine their connection in local schools. This lack of research shows why this study is needed. By exploring how stress management relates to performance, this study hopes to add to what we know about teacher effectiveness and to offer ideas to help improve education in the Philippines.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study was grounded in two foundational theories that provide a strong framework for understanding the dynamics between teachers' stress management and performance. These are the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping developed by Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman (1984), and the Job Performance Theory developed by John Campbell (1990).

The Transactional Model of Stress and Coping, developed by Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman (1984), characterizes stress as a dynamic process resulting from the interaction between a person and their surroundings. A key component of this approach is the concept of cognitive appraisal, in which a person initially performs a primary assessment to determine whether an experience they have encountered is stressful—posing a threat, challenge, or harm—irrelevant or benign-positive. If deemed stressful, a subsequent appraisal determines the person's coping mechanisms and options for handling the demands. When perceived external pressures outweigh one's coping mechanisms, stress triggers emotional, cognitive, and behavioral reactions. Problem-focused and emotion-focused coping are crucial for stress management since the model highlights that stress is subjective and differs from person to person based on their appraisal and coping mechanisms (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

Finally, work performance is viewed as an individual-level variable by John P. Campbell's Job Performance Theory (1990), which focuses on the actions that an individual takes that are pertinent to organizational objectives. By defining performance as behaviors or actions within an individual's control—whether observable acts or mental processes such as decision-making or problem-solving—Campbell distinguishes it from outcomes. Sales revenue is one example of an outcome influenced by individual performance and external factors beyond the employee's control. Campbell further stresses that work performance should be goal-oriented and aligned with the position's primary duties, excluding activities not tied to organizational goals. He also suggests that job performance is multifaceted, encompassing non-task-specific actions (such as training others) and task-specific behaviors (such as core duties). This paradigm emphasizes how knowledge, skills, motivation, and behavior contribute to performance, a complex construct that determines how effectively a person performs their job (Campbell, 1990).

Two interconnected theories serve as the foundation for this study. The transactional model of stress and coping offers a comprehensive framework for understanding how teachers cognitively appraise and respond to stressors in their work environment through coping strategies that influence their psychological well-being and functioning. And Campbell's theory situates work performance within the context of goal-directed behavior, influenced by knowledge, skills, and motivation—all of which are affected by a teacher's overall health and ability to cope with stress.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to examine the link between teachers' stress management and performance in public secondary schools in one district of a medium-sized division of a highly urbanized city in Negros Island Region during the school year 2023 - 2024. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, civil status, and level handled? What is the level of teachers' stress management? What is the level of teaching performance when grouped according to the aforementioned variables? Is there a significant difference in the teachers' stress-management levels when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables? Is there a significant difference in the teaching performance levels when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables? And, is there a significant relationship between the levels of teachers' stress management and performance?

Research Methodology

This section presents the research design, study respondents, instrumentation, data-gathering procedure, data analysis, and statistical tools, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design to determine the levels of teachers' stress management and teaching performance in one of the districts in a medium-sized division in a highly urbanized city in Negros Island Region, Philippines, during the School Year 2023-2024. The methodological approach of a descriptive study design, according to Enago (2023), is to observe, characterize, and record the traits, behaviors, or circumstances of a particular population or phenomenon without changing any factors. Its primary goal is to provide a comprehensive and accurate picture of the subject under study by identifying patterns, frequencies, trends, and relationships within the data. Descriptive design is appropriate for this study because it aims to discover what prevails in the present condition or relationships, the held opinions and beliefs, the processes and effects, and the developing trends. As part of the scientific method, the design entails monitoring and characterizing a subject's behavior without exerting any influence.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were 223 public school teachers out of a total population of 529. Since the number of respondents is significant, a stratified random sampling technique was used, using Cochran's formula (Cochran, 1977), a widely used method for estimating sample size in survey research when targeting proportions, to determine the sample size. Stratified random sampling is a probability sampling technique that divides a population into distinct subgroups, known as strata, based on shared characteristics such as age, gender, income, or education level. Stratified random sampling was used by dividing the population into homogeneous strata to ensure proportional representation and increased precision (Thomas, 2020).

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents according to their school.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

School	Population (N)	Sample (n)	Percentage (%)
A	64	27	12.10
B	59	25	11.15
C	22	9	4.16
D	15	6	2.84
E	37	15	6.99
F	63	26	11.91
G	26	11	4.92
H	57	24	10.78
I	35	15	6.62
J	56	24	10.59
K	30	13	5.67
L	35	15	6.62
M	30	13	5.67
TOTAL	529	223	100

Instrument

This study utilized a standardized survey questionnaire to determine teachers' stress management, while using secondary data on their teaching performance. The instrument consisted of two parts: Part I gathered respondents' profile information, including age, civil status, and level handled, while Part II consisted of the standardized instrument on teachers' stress management developed by Lazarus and Folkman (1984), which had undergone prior validity and reliability tests ensuring its appropriateness for measuring coping strategies. There were 10 items concentrated on assessing the respondents' stress management. And the work performance was based on their IPCRF for SY 2022-2023.

Data Gathering and Procedure

Upon the approval of the schools division superintendent, the questionnaire was administered to the target respondents. The questionnaires were gathered, recorded, and analyzed. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The encoded data were processed using SPSS.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1 to 3 employed a descriptive analytical scheme, using frequency counts and percentages as statistical tools to assess the profile of respondents, mean to assess the level of teachers' stress management and teaching performance. Objectives 4 and 5 used a comparative analytical scheme, applying the Mann-Whitney U test to determine significant differences in the levels of teachers' stress management and teaching performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Lastly, Objective 6 used Spearman rho to examine the significant relationship between the teachers' stress management levels and their performance.

Ethical Consideration

The study strictly observed ethical research standards by ensuring the protection of respondents' rights and welfare throughout the research process. The researcher secured written informed consent from the respondents prior to data collection. Participation in the study was voluntary, and respondents were clearly informed of the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. To minimize potential harm, the confidentiality of all responses was guaranteed, and the anonymity of the respondents was maintained during data gathering, analysis, and reporting. Moreover, the study complied with the provisions of Republic Act No. 10173, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, mandates the lawful, fair, and secure processing of personal and sensitive information (Republic of the Philippines, 2012).

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered to accomplish the predetermined objectives of this study.

Profile of Respondents

Table 2

Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 41 years old)	121	54.30
	Older (41 years old and above)	102	45.70
	Total	223	100
Civil Status	Single	68	30.50
	Married	155	69.50
	Total	223	100
Level Handled	1st Key Stage (Kindergarten - Grade 3)	74	33.20
	2nd Key Stage (Grade 4 - Grade 6)	67	30.00
	3rd Key Stage (Grade 7 - Grade 10)	82	36.80
	Total	223	100

Table 2 shows the age, civil status, and the level handled by the 223 teachers. For the variable age, 121 respondents (54.30%) are younger than 41 years old, whereas 102 respondents (45.70%) are considered part of the older group, who are 41 years old or older. This describes a teaching workforce that emphasizes moderation, and also indicates a youthful teaching workforce; however, there is also a considerable older cohort, suggesting a balanced distribution in terms of age, as well as experience and thoughtfulness.

Regarding civil status, most respondents are married, with a sample proportion of 155, or 69.50%, of the total sample. On the other hand, 68 respondents (30.50%) are single. This suggests that a good number of teachers are balancing these responsibilities, which will shape their views on professional development, workload, and work-life balance profundity.

Regarding the teaching level or key stage handled, the distribution is pretty even, although the 3rd Key Stage, which encompasses Grades 7 to 10, is the largest, with 82 respondents (36.80%) in that group. On the other hand, 74 respondents (33.20%) teach the 1st Key Stage (Kindergarten to Grade 3), and 67 respondents (30.00%) teach in the 2nd Key Stage (Grades 4 to 6). The data indicate that respondents sufficiently cater to all basic education levels. However, there appears to be some concentration in the upper grades, which have more subject specialization and academic rigor.

Level of Teachers' Stress Management

Table 3

Level of Teachers' Stress Management

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am...		
1. seeking emotional support from family and friends.	4.59	Very High Level
2. engaging in problem-solving to address the source of stress.	4.64	Very High Level
3. using relaxation techniques such as deep breathing or meditation.	4.79	Very High Level
4. engaging in physical exercise or activities to manage stress.	4.31	High Level
5. engaging in activities or hobbies you enjoy as a way to relax.	4.76	Very High Level
6. seeking professional help or counseling for stress management.	3.28	Moderate Level
7. using humor or positive reframing to cope with stress.	4.50	Very High Level
8. engaging in self-care activities to promote well-being.	4.50	Very High Level
9. setting clear goals and planning ahead to manage stress.	4.45	High Level

10. avoiding or minimizing exposure to stressful situations.	4.48	High Level
Overall Mean	4.43	High Level

Teachers' Stress Management Levels reveal various coping options against professional stress, as shown in Table 3. It has an average of 4.43 and is interpreted as a high level. Coming up next is Item 3-” using relaxation techniques such as deep breathing or meditation”-with a mean of 4.79, indicating a Very High Level. The least ranked item on the list was Item 6, "Seeking professional help or counseling for stress management," with a mean of 3.28, indicating a Moderate Level.

In the context of this study, the reluctance of teachers to seek psychological help for stress is deeply connected to cultural, socioeconomic, and systemic barriers in the education and healthcare sectors. Filipino culture has been said to promote the values of *hiya* (shame or embarrassment) and *tiis* (endurance or sacrifice), which usually prevent people, including teachers, from sharing their very personal struggles, especially when it comes to mental health issues. The stigma, sometimes wandering about, is that seeking professional psychological help connotes weakness and instability, an image that contradicts the archetype of the teacher as a self-sacrificing role model who stands tall against all adversities. Stigmatization thus causes numerous distressed teachers to bottle up their stress and rely on informal coping mechanisms such as praying, social gatherings, recreational pursuits, or mere endurance through hardship. Also, economic factors further contribute to the underutilization of counseling services. Many teachers take home very low incomes due to debts from loans and cannot consider the possibility of spending good money on mental health care.

Such observations also highlight the current state of those who are presently gathering. Following this, recent texts from Renshaw, Long, and Cook (2021) illustrate how teachers employ self-regulation techniques in their everyday activities but often avoid seeking formal mental health services due to stigma and a lack of resources. Skaalvik and Skaalvik 2023 (2023) highlight how institutional support structures, such as off-site counseling, serve to reduce burnout and increase resilience among teachers.

In addition, Mingoa (2017) explored stress levels and coping mechanisms among Metro Manila teachers, and it was found that teachers usually rely more on direct means (such as problem-solving) and palliative means (such as deep breathing and engaging in hobbies) while rarely seeking professional help.

Level of Teaching Performance

Table 4

Level of Teaching Performance When Grouped According to the Variables

Variable	Category	Mean	Interpretation
Age	Younger	4.65	Outstanding
	Older	4.68	Outstanding
Civil Status	Single	4.66	Outstanding
	Married	4.67	Outstanding
Level Handled	1st Key Stage	4.65	Outstanding
	2nd Key Stage	4.74	Outstanding
	3rd Key Stage	4.61	Outstanding

Table 4 presents figures for teaching performance when teachers were categorized by age, civil status, and the level handled. When grouped by age, younger and older teachers were performing excellently, with mean scores of 4.65 and 4.68, respectively. This implies that the quality of teaching is not influenced by experience or age and, thus, teachers at varying stages of their careers would be performing at equally high levels.

The performance of teachers grouped by civil status shows consistency: single teachers attained a mean score of 4.66, while married teachers achieved a mean score of 4.67, both indicating outstanding performance. This close comparison shows that conditions in private life, such as being married, do not detract from teachers' professional efficiency.

Level handled is yet another division in which outstanding performance is consistently achieved across the board. Teachers at the 2nd Key Stage registered the highest mean score of 4.74, followed by the 1st Key Stage, with a mean score of 4.65, and lastly, the 3rd Key Stage, with a mean score of 4.61. Such a slight difference could indicate variation in curriculum demands or in student motivation levels across different key stages. Still, it does not hinder teachers' overall high performance.

These results also align with those of Catarus and Guanzon (2025), which demonstrate that teachers consistently delivered outstanding work performance regardless of demographic factors such as age, civil status, and sex. Their studies have shown that, in general, performance ratings for public school teachers were very satisfactory and that the sex and civil status of teachers had no bearing on their work outcomes.

Furthermore, these results align with Maculada et al. (2024) who found that teachers maintain high performance regardless of their demographic background, with professionalism and commitment playing important roles. And, Doromal et al. (2024) also showed that teachers perform well even when their work situations and workloads change, demonstrating their adaptability and resilience.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Teachers' Stress Management

Table 5

Difference in the Level of Stress Management of Teachers When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	121	118.40	5396.500		0.103	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	102	104.41					
Civil Status	Single	68	122.82	4534.000		0.094	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	155	107.25					
Level Handled	1st Key Stage	74	116.32	3.733		0.155	0.05	Not Significant
	2nd Key Stage	67	99.46					
	3rd Key Stage	82	118.35					

Based on the table above, no significant differences were found among teachers grouped by age, civil status, and level of stress management. For younger teachers, the mean rank was 118.40, and for older teachers, the mean rank was 104.41, yielding a p-value of 0.103. Single teachers had a mean rank of 122.82, whereas married teachers had a mean rank of 107.25, with a p-value of 0.094. There were no significant differences recorded regarding stress management among teachers in the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd Key Stages ($p = 0.155$). Thus, the null hypothesis, stating “there is no significant difference between the levels of teachers’ stress management when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables” is hereby accepted.”

The lack of a significant difference in stress management levels among teachers, when grouped by age, civil status, and level handled, may be due to several cultural and contextual factors. First, teachers across demographic divides tend to share similar coping mechanisms based on artistic practices and values. These include strong family ties, community support, religious faith, and a collectivist orientation that encourages emotional sharing and resilience. So, it does not matter for stress purposes whether a teacher is young or old, single or married, or handling different key stages; social expectations and everyday experiences within the teaching profession give rise to similar methods of dealing with stress.

Moreover, teachers commonly resort to informal and accepted methods of stress relief, which include attending church activities, having leisure time watching *teleseryes* or gardening, and engaging in social activities; intriguingly, none of these can be categorized as unique to any demographic population. On the other hand, the spiritual orientation that permeates their way of life instills in them. Finally, everyday work-related matters, such as a heavy workload, scant resources, and high expectations encountered in the education system, may breed a more or less uniform sense of pressure that then finds its outlet in similar coping patterns across different teacher subgroups.

The research by Agyapong et al. (2022) substantiates the finding that there is no significant difference in the level of stress management among teachers when classified by age, civil status, or level of responsibility, while emphasizing the mediating role of emotional intelligence (EI) in teacher stress and burnout levels. Their study suggests that teachers and those with high emotional intelligence (EI) are better equipped to handle job demands and stress effectively, regardless of their demographic profile. This further means that stress resistance and coping ability are linked much more to emotional and psychological competencies than to personal variables such as age and marital status.

Comparative Analysis of the Level of Teaching Performance

Table 6

Difference in the Level of Teaching Performance of Teachers When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	121	105.43	5376.500		0.097	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	102	119.79					

Civil Status	Single	68	108.15	5008.500	0.555	Not Significant
	Married	155	113.69			
	1st Key Stage	74	107.70			
Level Handled	2nd Key Stage	67	147.88	33.953	0.000	Significant
	3rd Key Stage	82	86.56			

Table 6 displays differences in teaching work performance levels across age, civil status, and the level handled.

In terms of work performance, neither age nor civil status significantly affects teaching performance. Younger teachers (mean rank = 105.43) and older teachers (mean rank = 119.79) did not differ significantly when performance was considered a variable ($p = 0.097$). The same holds for single teachers (mean rank = 108.15) and married teachers (mean rank = 113.69), with a p -value of 0.555. Significant differences were found between teachers handling different levels (Kruskal-Wallis $H = 33.953$, $p = 0.000$). Teachers working in the 2nd Key Stage had the highest mean rank (147.88), indicating better performance than those working in the 1st Key Stage (mean rank = 107.70) and the 3rd Key Stage (mean rank = 86.56).

Thus, the null hypothesis stating, “there is no significant difference between the level of teachers’ work performance when grouped and compared according to the variables of age and civil status” is hereby accepted.” However, the null hypothesis stating, “there is no significant difference between the level of teachers’ work performance when grouped and compared according to the variable level handled” is hereby “rejected.”

This suggests that demographic factors do not substantially influence how teachers deliver their work. However, a significant difference emerges when grouped by the level being handled. Second Key Stage teachers (Grades 4–6) achieved the highest mean rank (147.88), while Third Key Stage teachers (Grades 7–10) scored the lowest (86.56). This suggests that middle-grade teachers may feel more affirmed in their instructional outcomes, while secondary teachers face greater challenges, including exam preparation, managing adolescent learners, and stricter accountability measures.

The 2nd Key Stage teachers may enjoy a balance between foundational instruction and student independence. At this stage, students are sufficiently capable of working independently with the content provided by their teachers. Therefore, teachers can employ a broader range of instructional strategies, monitor progress more effectively, and assess performance indicators more accurately. Correspondingly, curricular expectations at this stage may better reflect

measurable performance outcomes upon which professional development opportunities and recognition frameworks are based.

Conversely, 1st Key Stage teachers generally provide students with foundational skills, which may take time to show definite and positive effects or results, thereby negatively impacting perceived performance. On the other end of the spectrum, 3rd Key Stage teachers, who are often subject specialists across different grades, may face more content-heavy demands combined with administrative duties, reducing the time available for collaborative or integrative teaching approaches and thereby negatively impacting their performance ratings.

Consistent with Klassen and Chiu's (2020) research, teacher performance depends on teaching level, with middle-level teachers tending to report higher self-efficacy and performance, which may be linked to the developmental appropriateness of the curriculum and teacher-student relations.

Relational Analysis Between the Levels of Teachers' Stress Management and Teaching Performance

Table 7

Relationship between the Level of Teachers' Stress Management and Performance

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of stress Management	-0.003	0.969	0.05	Not Significant
Level of Teaching Performance				

Table 7 shows an insignificant negative correlation (-0.003) between stress management among teachers and their work performance, with a p-value of 0.969, indicating a statistically negligible relationship at the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis stating, "There is no significant relationship between the levels of teachers' stress management and work performance" is hereby accepted."

It is implied that the ability of teachers to manage stress does not have an immediate influence on their work performance, whether perceived or reported. It takes into account several considerations relevant to cultural, spiritual, and professional contexts. Filipino teachers have been regarded as resilient and vocation-oriented, often grounded in the artistic value of *bayanihan* (communal unity) and an ingrained belief that teaching is a calling, not merely a profession. With that kind of motivation, teachers can deliver consistent work performance despite stress. Additionally, they tend to engage in culturally grounded forms of coping, such as

playing mahjong, caring for plants (*plantita*), watching K-dramas, singing karaoke, and simply bonding with family and friends, through which they can relax and balance their emotions. Another consideration is the profoundly spiritual nature of many teachers, which is created in a way that advances their burnout resistance. To practice praying, attend Mass, or participate in devotional reading for an uplifting spirit, they get strengthened internally by knowing their task has meaning. In an ad hoc manner, these personal and informal channels for emotional and spiritual sustenance keep them grounded and committed despite stressors and help them remain focused on their professional duties.

These results support the study by Bontilao (2024) at the Teresian Daughters of Mary-Managed Schools High School Department, which found that even though teachers were using stress management interventions on a regular basis, there was no significant relationship between stress management and job performance. According to statistical analyses, stress management was found to have an almost negligible correlation, indicating that it does not significantly affect teachers' job performance. Additionally, none of the specific areas of stress management had an impact on performance, again suggesting that even effective stress management did not result in enhanced job performance in this case.

Likewise, the study's results support the research by Gudelos and Mabitad (2025), who conducted a mixed-methods descriptive-correlational study in a senior high school in Cebu City, Philippines. They studied work-related stress, heavy workload, and teaching performance through validated stress questionnaires, workload measures, standardized performance evaluation, and qualitative interviews. The results implied that moderate stress and load caused no problem in the teachers' performance; hence, stress and workload were insignificantly predictive of teaching performance, which remained firm and resilient.

Conclusion:

The study revealed that teachers demonstrated strong use of stress management and high levels of teaching performance; thus, educators were able to carry out their work and maintain their own self-preservation and instructional effectiveness. Teachers often made good use of adaptive coping strategies, such as relaxation exercises, problem-solving, and social support, while resorting to serious professional psychological help the least. These findings highlight that Filipino teachers still employ inherent coping strategies and personal resilience to manage occupational stress.

According to the outcomes, there was no significant difference in stress-coping strategies or teaching efficiency between teachers classified by age and civil status. There was a significant difference in teaching efficiency by level handled, with teachers in the intermediate grades performing relatively better. Contextual factors related to teaching situations, including the demands of the curriculum and the characteristics of the learner, seemed to have a greater impact on performance than demographics.

The research has established that there is no significant relationship between stress management and teaching performance, suggesting that performance remains consistently high across different stress management levels. The above implies that a culture of strong motivations, such as attraction, resilience, and moral virtues, like commitment, runs, and charity, will keep teachers and teacher-practitioners motivated enough to continue their professional responsibilities. Thus, although stress management skills are essential for maintaining general well-being, they do not directly predict teaching practices; that is, the study underscores the intricate path of teaching effectiveness or performance in the cultural context of Philippine education.

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